

IPBES TCA. Corpus of literature on transformative change / IPBES transformative change assessment

Code: IPBES_TCA_Corpus

Versioning 03: (24.01.2025)

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10251349

Full Report: 10.5281/zenodo.11447691

Technical document/repository: 10.5281/zenodo.11447691

Project leaders

Rainer M Krug (rainer@krugs.de), Sebastián Villasante (sebastian.villasante@usc.es), Sergio Lambertucci (slambertucci@comahue-conicet.gob.ar), Victoria Reyes Garcia (Victoria.Reyes@uab.cat), Arun Agrawal (arunagra@umich.edu), Karen O'Brien (karen.obrien@sosgeo.uio.no), Lucas Alejandro Garibaldi (lgaribaldi@unrn.edu.ar).

Researchers

Lynne Shannon (lynne.shannon@uct.ac.za), Chuan Liao (cl824@cornell.edu), Yves Zinngrebe (yves.zinngrebe@ufz.de), Niki Frantzeskaki (n.frantzeskaki@uu.nl), Janita Gurung (janita.gurung@icimod.org), Julia Mildorfova Leventon (leventon.j@czechglobe.cz), Fern Wickson (fern.wickson@uit.no), Oonsie Biggs (oonsie@sun.ac.za), Elena Bennett (elena.bennett@mcgill.ca), Rafael Calderón-Contreras (rcalderon@cua.uam.mx), Hannah Gosnell (gosnellh@oregonstate.edu), Mariana Cantu Fernandez (mariana.cantufernandez@un.org), Edward Carr (edcarr@clarku.edu), Karina Benessaiah (karinaben@gmail.com).

Knowledge and Data TSU members

Rainer M Krug (rainer@krugs.de), Aidin Niamir (aidin.niamir@senckenberg.de), Renske Gudde (renske.gudde@senckenberg.de).

Data curator(s)

Rainer M Krug (rainer@krugs.de), Camille Guibal (camille.guibal@umontpellier.fr).

Description

The review corresponds to the IPBES transformative change assessment. The IPBES Scoping document for the transformative change assessment describes that the assessment should inform decision-makers on options to implement transformative change in order to achieve the 2050 Vision for Biodiversity and the Sustainable Development Goals. The assessment provides evidence on what transformative change is, visions for transformative change, how transformative change happens, what are the barriers to transformative change and what are the options for achieving the 2050 Vision for Biodiversity. In this context, a review of literature focused on building an overarching corpus of references on transformative change was conducted and is further described below.

Process overview

Summary

The literature search for the assessment corpus was conducted using search terms provided by the experts and refined in cooperation with the Data and Knowledge task force.

The search was conducted using [OpenAlex](#), scripted from [R](#) to use the [API](#). Search terms for the following searches were defined:

- Transformative Change - 18,844,396 results
- Nature / Environment - 26,116,505 results

The final number of works in of the corpus is 4,227,131.

To assess the quality of the corpus, sets of key papers were selected by the experts of each chapter / sub-chapter to verify if the corpus includes these most relevant papers. A total of 241 papers were submitted, with duplicates. The list was composed of 146 after deleting duplicates. These key papers were selected per chapter / sub-chapter to ensure that the corpus is representative of each chapter.

Complete Data Management Report

The complete data management report includes all code used to conduct the searches and to assess the quality of the corpus as well as the key papers provided. It is fully reproducible and does not require any additional data.

The report concludes that the search term definitions for *transformative change* as well as *nature / environment* do include the key papers provided by the experts.

The full report can be found via the full report DOI: **10.5281/zenodo.11447691**

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